

A Theoretical Study on Yogic Tools to Defeat Procrastination

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Abstract

Procrastination, putting off tasks despite knowing their importance, can have negative consequences. Research shows that 80%-95% of college students procrastinate, of which about 75% procrastinate. Defined as the deliberate delay of tasks, procrastination is known to be a significant psychological challenge. Valuable information about procrastination and its remedies is provided in our ancient Indian Yoga literature. Yoga, which is very old, provides valuable information about procrastination and its remedies, asanas, pranayama, and meditation benefit the mind, body, and overall health. Texts such as the Bhagavad Gita and the teachings of Maharishi Patanjali emphasize that inattention and laziness are obstacles to progress - the key aspects of procrastination. Similarly, the poems of Sant Kabir Das emphasize the importance of timely action to avoid missed opportunities.

Modern research has proved that yoga is an effective remedy for procrastination. The practice of yoga improves brain functioning, memory, and cognitive abilities and helps prevent age-related decline. Yoga increases the levels of gamma-aminobutyric acid (GABA), which calms the brain, reduces anxiety, and addresses the underlying psychological causes of procrastination. Pranayama purifies the blood, strengthens the respiratory system, and increases mental clarity through techniques such as alternate nostril breathing. Meditation can reduce procrastination substantially by improving concentration, self-regulation, and emotional stability.

In conclusion, thus, yoga offers a holistic approach to overcoming procrastination that promotes both physical and mental health. Incorporating yoga into your daily life can be a transformative strategy to combat procrastination and achieve personal and professional goals.

Keywords: Procrastination, Delay, Procrastination in Yog Sutra, Procrastination in Shrimadbhagwat Gita, Yoga

Introduction:

Everyone knows the importance of time but even after knowing it, we keep postponing our important tasks. Sometimes it becomes so terrible that its result emerges in front of us in the form of terrible losses. This problem of procrastination has been called procrastination in research etc.

Not being able to find time for your daily tasks or not starting the work on time even after knowing it is necessary is procrastination. The meaning of the word “procrastination” comes from the Latin words “pro: ahead, forward “and “crastinus: tomorrow”. (Thye Miriam, 2016).

Procrastination is so deeply ingrained in every behaviour and habit that nearly all of us want to get everything done on time, but for some people it has become a way of life. Estimates suggest that 80%-95% of college students procrastinate (Ellis, 1977) (O'Brien, 2002), approximately 75% consider themselves procrastinators (Potts, 1987).

Procrastination defined by Researchers:

The definition for procrastination is the delaying of a task that was originally planned despite expecting to be worse off for the delay (van Eerde, 2003).

Some people report regular rates of task delays or incompleteness across many situations in their life - a tendency known as procrastination. (Ferrari J. , 1995) (Ferrari J. &., 2000).

Yoga literature: identification of procrastination and remedy

Yoga, an ancient Indian practice that works on the mind and brain, has become popular in Western cultures in the last few decades (Saper RB, 2004). Yoga is a multifaceted spiritual practice, one of its many positive effects is improved health and well-being. The components of yoga that are commonly applied for health benefits are asanas (physical postures), pranayama (regulated breathing) and meditation. Asanas in yoga may seem like a physical exercise, but it is more than an exercise.

व्याधिस्थ्यानसंशयप्रमादालस्याविरतिभ्रान्तिदर्शनालब्धभूमिकत्वानवस्थितत्वानि
चित्तविक्षेपास्तेऽन्तरायाः॥

vyādhi-styāna-samśāya-pramaṇa-alāśya-avīratibhrānti-darśana-alabdā-bhūmiktva-
anavasthittvāni chitta-vikṣepāḥ te'antarayah (Patanjalikrit, 2019)

Meaning: carelessness, laziness , non-abstention , false perception , failing to obtain stages of practice and inability to stay in that state - These distractions of the mind are the impediments.

In this “Pramāda” carelessness or negligence, which can lead to mistakes in practice or lack of commitment.

“Alasya” - laziness or lethargy, which is a common form of procrastination and delays progress.

Maharishi Patanjali specifically mentions “Pramāda”. It is closely related to procrastination, as it interferes with the performance of tasks, etc. Negligence can be taken as avoiding necessary tasks, postponing practice, and failing to correct mistakes.

तमस्त्वज्ञानजं विद्धि मोहनं सर्वदेहिनाम् ।

प्रमादालस्यनिद्राभिस्तन्निबध्नाति भारत ॥

Tamas tv ajñāna-jam viddhi mohanam sarva-dehinam Pramādālasya-nidrābhis tan
nibadhnāti bhārata (Shrimad Bhagwat Gita)

Meaning: O Arjun, tamo guṇa, which is born of ignorance, is the cause of illusion for the embodied souls. It deludes all living beings through negligence, laziness, and sleep.

This verse describes the nature and effects of Tamas, one of the three Gunas (qualities or tendencies) that influence human behavior and consciousness. Tamas arises from ignorance and has a deluding effect on all beings. It binds individuals in this way. Pramad or carelessness is directly related to procrastination. Laziness or sloth, i.e. lying in one place without thinking, is complete procrastination and manifests as an unwillingness to act or a tendency to delay tasks, often leading to procrastination.

This verse focuses on the effects and effects of how these two aspects of Tamas bind human beings, preventing or distracting them from achieving clarity and progress in their spiritual and worldly endeavors. Pramad and laziness described in the Bhagavad Gita play a significant role in hindering progress by promoting procrastination. When someone is careless or negligent, tasks are put off to be done later or are done incompletely, which is a common trait of Tamas in humans.

काल करे सो आज कर, आज करै सो अब |

पल में परलय होगी, बहुरी करेगा कब ||

Kāl kare so āj kar, āj karai so ab | Pal mein pralaya hoegi, bahuri karegā kab (Marden, 2016)

This famous doha by Sant Kabir Das Ji emphasizes on procrastination. In this, we are asked to do our tasks on time. Often, we procrastinate thinking that we have more time. Kabir is against such a mindset in this couplet and suggests that we should move our plans forward and execute them as soon as possible. Whatever you intend to do today, do it now.

If you keep putting off your tasks, a moment may come when it will be too late to complete them. Kabir questions the procrastinator, highlighting the potential loss of opportunity if the task is put off.

Kabir's doha directly addresses the issue of procrastination. The eternal wisdom he imparts is that putting off tasks often leads to missed opportunities or work left incomplete. The call to take immediate action is a powerful antidote to procrastination. By stressing the urgency of "now," Kabir inspires a sense of responsibility and awareness of time management.

Yoga: Weapon to defeat Procrastination

Yoga is a very old practice from India that helps people feel good about their body and mind. It helps you concentrate and relax. People have found that doing yoga can help them stay healthy and happy, especially if they suffer from laziness etc. It fills them with energy.

Patanjali's eight limbs of yoga (Ashtanga Yoga) include asanas (postures) as the third limb, designed to exercise every muscle, gland, and nerve, promoting physical and mental freedom (BKS, 1997).

Doing yoga is like exercising your brain. It helps your brain form new connections and strengthen them, which can make you better at learning and remembering things. Just like lifting weights strengthens your muscles, yoga makes your brain stronger. Using special machines that take pictures of the brain, scientists have found that people who do yoga often have larger parts of the brain that help them think and remember things. As we get older, these parts of the brain usually get smaller, but doing yoga helps keep them bigger. This means that doing yoga can help older people keep their memory and thinking skills sharp as they age. Studies have found that doing yoga and meditation can make your brain work better and help you think, remember, learn, make decisions, and react faster and more accurately.

The advantage of yoga is more than just physical activity. Previous studies show that the level of GABA in the brain, which helps the brain calm, is increasing immediately after yoga sessions. The increase in GABA is short. A certain level of GABA indicates that yoga starts to stabilize them to low -level people. The measurement of mood and anxiety indicates that yoga is calm and restored (Chris C. Streeter, 2010).

Pranayama: Breathing Control

Different pranayama has positive impact on mental health. The psychological reason behind the procrastination can be treated through Pranayama or Breathing techniques in Yoga. Alternate nostril breathing practice also known as nadi shodhana pranayama helps to purifies the blood and strengthen the respiratory system. It increase the mental clarity and keeps the mind calm, increased ability of concentration (Vindha Paul, 2015).

Dhyana: Meditation a perfect remedy

Meditation substantially reduces procrastination, as evidenced by the significantly decreased procrastination rate observed in meditation participants. This reduction is associated with increased concentration and deeper thought processes developed through meditation, leading to a deeper understanding of one's inner feelings, values, and intrinsic motivation. The ability to self-regulate is important, particularly in relation to attention, emotions, and self-awareness. Students who meditate are able to better focus on desired tasks without being distracted by less important tasks because their confidence increases and anxiety decreases. Additionally, their higher emotional regulation allows them to view upsetting emotional situations as less disruptive, allowing them to focus and stick to planned tasks. These results are consistent with the current literature on the positive effects of meditation, although larger studies are needed to further validate these results (Miriam Thye, 2016)

Discussion:

As evidence, we have seen from ancient Indian scriptures and modern research etc. that procrastination is a subject of psychology. It is a dialogue between the mind and the

intellect which ultimately works negatively for any person. Because any person who is procrastinating only harms himself. From the study, we found that procrastination is not a problem of today, but it has been present since ancient times. At the same time, the practice of yoga which includes asanas, pranayama, meditation etc. strengthens the psychology of man i.e. mental power, which helps a person to defeat procrastination. This type of research should be done between procrastination and other parameters of yoga. Right now it seems that work on this subject is still pending.

Conclusion:

Yoga is an effective remedy for procrastination and helps you stay physically and mentally healthy. It engages cognitive functions such as concentration, relaxation, memory, and decision-making. Yoga increases GABA levels in the brain, which promotes relaxation and reduces anxiety that often leads to procrastination. Pranayama improves mental toughness and concentration, while meditation increases self-regulation and intrinsic motivation, increasing concentration at work and reducing distractions. Overall, the holistic approach of yoga helps people overcome procrastination and achieve higher productivity.

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